

Species 1: *H. charitonia*

NOT test

Species 2: *H. peruvianus*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.017

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

Species 1: *H. charitonia*

NDT test

Species 2: *H. peruvianus*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.24

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

